

STAND N9

EFFECTS OF ADJUNCTIVE RH-TRANSFERRING ON SUSCEPTIBILITY AND EMERGENCE OF RESISTANCE IN GRAM-NEGATIVE PATHOGENS

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Conference Topic: Biomedicine

Keywords: *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, antibiotic resistance, transferrin

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Human pathogens have experienced selective pressure from antibiotics for nearly 80 years. The high speed of antibiotic resistance formation in nosocomial bacteria together with overuse of antibiotics have promoted the current multidrug resistance crisis. The problem is especially important for Russian healthcare, where the majority of isolated clinical strains of *A. baumannii* are drug-resistant: 93% of them are resistant to Cefoperazone, 61,2% - to Amicacin, 51,9% - to Levofloxacin [1]. We attempted to decrease the emergence of resistant mutants using a novel combination of antibiotics with recombinant human transferrin (rh-transferrin). We hypothesized that rh-transferrin, which functions by passively starving the bacteria of iron needed for microbial replication [2], would exert less selective pressure as compared to traditional antibiotics. It has been reported in previous studies that transferrin has broad antimicrobial effects *in vitro* against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and fungal pathogens [3].

The main goal of this project is to study the *in vitro* and *in vivo* effect of adjunctive transferrin on susceptibility and emergence of resistance in the Gram-negative pathogens *Acinetobacter baumannii* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

Materials and Methods: Time kill assays were done using ciprofloxacin or meropenem with and without transferrin. Viability was assessed at 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, and 24 hours for *A. baumannii* and at 1, 4, and 24 hours for *K. pneumoniae*. The assay was done using either resazurin (cellular metabolic readout) or quantitative culturing. Antibiotic resistant mutants were selected by passaging a high inoculum of bacteria in sub-lethal concentrations of antibiotic for 24 hours or by serial passaging lower inocula of bacteria for 20 days with or without rh-transferrin. C3HeB/FeJ mice were infected IV with 2×10^7 CFU of *A. baumannii* LAC-4 strain and mice were administered a sub-therapeutic dose of ciprofloxacin (50 mg/kg BID) with and without transferrin (100 mg/kg).

Results: The time-kill assays for both bacterial species showed no interaction between the antibiotics and rh-transferrin *in vitro* for most strains. Mutant selection for 24 hours and 20 days demonstrated decrease in mutant emergence in the group treated with combination of rh-transferrin and antibiotics compared to antibiotics alone. The 20 day passage experiment selected for mutants with an extremely high level of resistance. LD100 for all strains in C3HeB/FeJ mice were defined. *In vivo* efficacy experiments will begin soon with combination therapy.

Conclusions: We found that transferrin containing therapeutic regimens suppressed the emergence of resistance *in vitro*, and is promising as an adjunct to antibiotic therapy.

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